

"The Impact of Digital Advertising on Consumer Behavior in Online Education Markets: A Study of India and Neighboring Countries"

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Abstract

This research paper investigates the influence of digital advertising on consumer purchasing patterns within the realm of online courses and explores the efficacy of digital communication as a tool for advertising. The study provides practical and strategic guidance for digital advertisers, marketers, and brand communicators, with a specific emphasis on major online education markets, particularly in India and its neighboring countries. Employing a qualitative research approach, the research utilizes the Prisma technique to scrutinize existing literature and delve into consumer perceptions of online media platforms for the promotion of online courses. The resulting insights offer valuable knowledge for digital marketers and brand communicators seeking to excel in advertising, branding, and endorsing online education. Furthermore, the paper underscores the challenges and opportunities intrinsic to advertising and promoting online education in the digital age, emphasizing the critical importance of effectively harnessing available tools.

Keywords: Digital advertising, consumer behaviour, branding, and media promotional strategies, online courses.

Introduction

The growth of e-commerce in India has been attributed to many things including population growth with more people with access to 4G internet connectivity, increasing smartphone and digital device use, and the availability of more online products. India is gradually gaining a foothold as the leading economy in the Asia-Pacific region with e-commerce being one of the leading industries.

Digital advertisement communication in India is applied in various ways across the business world. Some of these applications include order tracking for freight systems, online payment systems, and online banking.

The power of digital marketing allows all consumers and companies to remove geophysical obstacles which make them all potential clients and suppliers. It is known for its ability to communicate and make transactions wherever and whenever possible. In India, digital marketing is a booming career. In a country that has a fast-growing economy, many more can be expected to get into a career in digital marketing.

The growth of digital marketing trends has an impact on digital advertising communication marketing and advertising (Maheshwari, P., 2019). As businesses adopt digital content creation for their advertisement needs, competition on the online space has increased. Businesses have had to develop competitive strategies to stand out in the ever-growing online space.

In today's world it is hard to imagine daily life without the internet. The internet has an effect on every facet of contemporary life and as device and internet use continue their steady climb, the future of digital communication looks promising. Businesses may however have to remain innovative to take advantage of the opportunities in the growing online market.

The smartphone revolution has put a mini-computer on the palm of people maximizing internet consumption. The smartphone industry has grown exponentially and made technology more affordable to the masses.

The International Journal of the Advanced Research Foundation has revealed that India was on the verge of its golden age in connectivity and e-commerce between 2013 and 2018 with a few sectors most likely to experience rapid growth (Suginraj, M., 2017). These sectors include internet advertisement, content management, and e-commerce.

Today, digital advertisement communication industry continues growing at a rapid pace influenced by the development and use of communication tools. There has been a rise in the level of trust over the internet and people can now more than ever make credible online transactions. Low smartphone costs and around 600 million internet users create a fascinating chance to sell to the growing population.

Online courses have come a long way from a buzzword in 2016 to an integral part of every learning system. In today's world, online learning is blossoming as a career builder by favourable government policy.

Online courses are readily available to people with an internet connection. Various platforms offer seamless learning and skills development. Udemy, one of the leading sites offers a chance to master Industry ready skills like graphic designing, animation, Motion graphics 3-D graphics, etc. These courses are also affordable with introductory sessions ranging from \$5 to \$50.

Mass Media, specifically digital media is bringing drastic changes in the pattern of promotion, consumption and sharing information in the present times. This purpose of the study's is to review the literature on the function of online media in selling courses. This study would like to suggest the strategies for implementation to digital advertising, marketers, public relation personnel's, educational corporate communicators and content writers post-covid arena.

Research Methodology

This paper performed the systematic literature review by using Prisma approach. A systematic literature review has two main steps: (1) pick inclusion criteria and (2) select repositories and papers (McLean & Antony, 2014). This research focused on the impact of digital advertising on consumer buying behaviour of online courses and examining digital advertising strategies adopted by popular digital platforms offering online courses, for which it searched all the relevant papers based on prescribed inclusion criteria as mentioned below.

The Inclusion Criteria

The study followed the Campbell Collaboration Users Group (2019) approach for selecting the research papers at different steps by involving five field experts, including media professionals and academicians. This study adopted the inclusion criteria approach by Kim, Bai, Kim, and Chon (2018) as follows. Broadly, it investigated the digital media-specific journals, journal name, research paper title, subject area, and review timeframe. Broadly, it categorizes the inclusion criteria into three parts such as the following:

1. All the research articles related to the impact of media published between 2000 and 2021 were included in the search criteria.
2. Existing literature from the field of “digital media, media studies and online advertising” was only taken into consideration. The areas were chosen seeing the relevancy of the subject and scope of the given research article.

Research Database and Article Selection

The two authentic sources of gathering quality research articles of the present, namely, Elsevier Scopus and Web of Science were used to gather papers. These are the two authentic sources of gathering quality research articles. After selecting the database, an advance search was performed by using a different combination of keywords. The words ‘digital advertising and online courses’ were kept constant for all searches. The other word combinations used along with that were ‘online media and education’, ‘academic blogs’, ‘digital media in education’, ‘Asian media in online education’, ‘digital media and advertising’, ‘online websites on consumers’ and ‘online advertising and educational courses consumption’. Next, the collected research articles were searched for further papers using their citations.

The articles collected from the above stage were double screened using Prisma approach as shown in Fig.1. The aforementioned steps led to the collection of 164 articles from the research. Initial screening of the research papers resulted in removal of 13 duplicate papers. In the next stage, the two subject experts read 151 remaining documents. The experts reviewed the papers based on their title and abstract. In this process, 94 research papers based on expert opinions were removed. The exclusion was based on the title of article ($n = 58$), abstract of the articles ($n = 27$) and duplicate articles ($n = 9$). In the next stage, 57 remaining articles were reviewed by two subject experts and one research scholar. The detailed study

resulted in the exclusion of 39 research articles based on the relevancy of subject area and inclusion criteria. Hence, 16 research articles were found suitable for further analysis and critical review.

Figure 1. Selection Criteria of a Research Paper Based on “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (Prisma) Approach”

Review of Literature

The section divided the 16 papers into three sections for further review based on the subject area. The topics were focussed on the impact of digital advertising on consumer buying behaviour. The following section analyzed the papers based on these three subject classifications.

Consumer Behaviour in Digital Environment

The most common online activities are sending and receiving emails, doing financial transactions via the internet, searching for information, and being exposed to content found online. Regardless of the kind of products, the Internet, mobile devices, and social media all provide consumers with access to knowledge and entertaining information in a participatory manner (Kotler 2000). Significant progress has been made in developing new tools and platforms. Customers may now do online research, analyze, and make purchases for various products, including but not limited to apparel, appliances, electronics, groceries, insurance, and even huge products like automobiles and houses.

Sindhya (2013) concluded that although digital advertisement typically offers information that covers all personality types, certain statements by customers neglect some of these particulars and instead depend on the public advertisement and personal knowledge to evaluate marketed goods. On the other hand, some customers wait to make product purchasing choices until marketing statements are shown to be accurate.

According to Khusbhoo Makwana (2019), how people acquire, make use of, and dispose of goods and services has altered due to digital advertising. Her research attempts to analyze this phenomenon since India's structured online taxi sector has seen a surge in demand over the last several years. Organizations must spend more money on new media for their advertising budget than conventional media. The current research focuses on a longitudinal analysis of the impact that digital marketing has on customer purchase behavior. The study revealed that women would understand these integrated taxi services' safety aspects and innovations online.

In their research titled "Sex disparity wise analysis of impulse-oriented purchasing behavior patterns and exploratory research in Central India," Vishal Khasgiwala and Monica Sainy (2020) tested a pulsating purchasing pattern. Most people are propelled by impulses of human activity that are aroused biochemically and mentally. Beatty and Ferrell described impulsive purchasing as a matter of urgency that either purchase a certain product category or meet a specific necessity without any pre-shopping purpose.

Consumer behaviour in buying online courses

Most significantly, the individual's motivation in learning the various courses plays a key part in influencing the various knowledge among the students. Students' interests have a key role in influencing a wide variety of risks associated with the technical infrastructure of the education sector, particularly in the online learning environment for various courses. There are a lot of risks involved, particularly in the case of online learning for various courses, which has become obligatory depending on the efficacy of the person. When unauthorized users require it, learning materials for various online courses have become accessible (Peruski and Mishra, 2004).

According to Anita Prescila J and Shanthi (2011), consumer satisfaction is important in their essay "Fulfilling requests of retail customers with special importance to Chennai-based retail establishments." The factors affecting customer delays, health, support, and convenience are insignificant compared to store-related variables such as interior and external framework, class of commodity and range, and competent administration.

Rachel Sullivan (2012) outlines how customers are cynically depicted as the newest religion with its temples via publicities even before they go to the retail establishment to purchase and exhibit at the front. The experiment conducted by Lindstorm is discussed in this study. It demonstrates how religious people reacted when shown pictures of religious symbols while simultaneously seeing images linked with powerful brands.

Lahoti and Jacob (2013) demonstrated that the success of a brand in the rural Indian market is as unpredictable as the weather. It has always been difficult to calculate the rural market. Several brands that had every opportunity to be successful failed terribly. Chance has a far larger role in the success of rural businesses than

any other factor. So, to comprehend the dynamics of the rural market, it is necessary to analyze the behavior of the rural people.

According to Harfoushi et al. (2013), the web network is evolving into a contemporary online shopping method for different goods or services. Everyone has the right to access the items they choose to purchase. Nonetheless, today's Internet plays a more significant role than ever in promoting shopping. Shopping is now only a click away thanks to the network, which streamlines making purchases. "Online shopping" is a brand-new idea. Customers may purchase the products or services of the salesperson right away without any contact between intermediaries. The Internet and other advertising forms, such as television and catalogs, are efficient marketing tools.

In the user's character, actions, and attitude, Johar (2015) described the fundamental aspects of decision-making. Every customer transaction follows a certain cycle of resolutions. Customer chooses to purchase and rate goods and services that they discover via digital ads in addition to carrying out arduous chores. Only very lately has research been done on making purchasing choices, which is a more complicated process.

According to Awan et al. (2016), these variables also support the need for digital ads, the pleasure of ads, the dominance of ads, and advertising promotion. We help mold and enhance customers' shopping patterns, a positive indicator for advertising and organizations seeking awareness. The study framework also displayed the outcomes, demonstrating that ads considerably impacted consumers' purchasing patterns and widened their decision-making. Given the conclusions of our analyses, this research is unquestionably useful to marketers and advertising agencies in marketing their goods.

Sai Vijay T. M. S. Balaji, and Notwithstanding (2019) the convenience offered, digital advertising is not India's most prevalent purchase method. The study shows an increasing transfer from crowded stores globally to the digital marketing layout with one click. To learn why some people purchase online rather than in physical stores, a survey of 150 customers was carried out. This survey included both web users and non-web users. The results demonstrate that Indian consumers can purchase online due to convenience and time savings, but protection and privacy concerns prohibit them from doing so.

Traditional advertisement and marketing tactics have been surpassed by digital marketing. As discovered by (Kayumovich, K. O., & Annamuradovna, F. S., 2020) in the paper, "The main convenience of internet marketing from traditional marketing. To determine whether or not digital marketing tools are effective and helpful in obtaining results, companies in Singapore have put them to the test

Harold W. Berkman and Christopher Gilson (2021) are described as having "unified" behaviors in their purchasing decision, meaning they make decisions and evaluate things based on the information they take in. The phrase "unified behavior patterns" refers to actions in its widest definition. Even if the construction of an attitude and other subjective internal actions like these cannot be viewed, they are nonetheless behavioral. A person's attitudes, ideas, wants, views, and actions are interrelated in the buying network. According to the study, "consumer characteristics continue to be a disciplined youth, and accessible employment has just been common during the last 15 years or more."

Digital communication as an advertising tool

An Analytical Study of Digital Advertising Techniques and Assessing Its Effectiveness was the subject of research conducted by Saxenaa, K., and Mittal, S. According to the findings of this study, digital advertising strategies such as "search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, e-mail marketing, and direct marketing" have become very common as a result of the association between technical innovation and online advertising. Consequently, the need for Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), benchmarks against which an e-commerce company's performance may be evaluated, has also emerged. Once determined, KPIs have the potential to not only assist an e-commerce company in developing an effective marketing strategy in this fast-paced digital world but also to contribute to the overall improvement of the effectiveness of the business by providing tools to measure the actual performance of the company in comparison to the estimated standards

Content generation and management is one of the talents and professions required to expand the sector further, even if digital advertising drives the digitization process in India's digital economy (Rathaur, K. S., & Agarwal, A. K., 2019). The recent decision by the government to demonetize notes with a face value.

To encourage digital transactions, brands across various industries have raised their marketing sector spending. E-wallet companies have upped their digital marketing efforts and capitalized on new online consumer bases (Taneja, G., & Vij, S., 2019). The fact that the vast majority of online purchases are made with cash-on-delivery alternatives has slowed down the growth of digital communication tools, which is one of the rising challenges.

Table 1. Consumer Behaviour in Digital Environment

SI. No.	Author	Year	Location	Objective	Research Technique	Findings and Suggestions
1	Kotler	2000	Europe	To do online research, analyze, and make purchases for various products.	Quantitative and Qualitative both	Regardless of the kind of products, the Internet, mobile devices, and social media all provide consumers with access to knowledge and entertaining information in a participatory manner
2	Sindhya	2013	Asia	To study the relationship between public advertisement and personal knowledge.	Exploratory(framing)	The study concluded that “Although digital advertisement typically offers information that covers all personality types, certain statements by customers neglect some of these particulars and instead depend on the public advertisement and personal knowledge to evaluate marketed goods”.
3	Makwana	2019	India	This study's goal was to assess how people acquire, make use of, of goods and services due to digital advertising	Survey Study	The study recommended “the use of digital advertising based on integrated taxi services' safety aspects of women and”.
4	Khasgiwala & Sainy	2020	India	Sex disparity wise analysis of impulse-	Exploratory Study	The studies concluded that Most people are propelled by impulses of human

				oriented purchasing behaviour patterns and exploratory research in Central India		activity that are aroused biochemically and mentally
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Table 2. Consumer behaviour in buying online courses

Sl. No.	Author	Year	Location	Objective	Research Technique	Findings and Suggestions
1	Peruski & Mishra	2004	India	To undertake research on the individual's motivation in learning the various courses	Critical review	Findings suggest that there are a lot of risks involved, particularly in the case of online learning for various courses, which has become obligatory depending on the efficacy of the person.
2	Prescila & Shanthi	2011	Europe	To examine the factors affecting customer s	Qualitative and quantitative research	It is advised that consumer satisfaction is important fulfilling requests of retail customers.
3	Rachel & Sullivan	2012	USA	To outline the pulsating behaviour of the customers	Experiment Study	The study demonstrated the reactions of the customers watching religious symbols linked with powerful brands.
4	Lahoti & Jacob	2013	India	To analyze the behaviour of rural customers of India	Survey Study	The findings proved the success of a brand in the rural Indian market is as unpredictable as the weather.
5	Harfoushi	2013	Europe	To investigate the role of advertising	Content Analysis	The findings suggest that the web network is

				forms, such as television and catalogues as efficient marketing tools.		evolving into a contemporary online shopping method for different goods or services.
6	Johar	2015	India	To explore the making purchasing choices	Content Analysis	The study propounded, customer's character, actions, and attitude as the fundamental aspects of decision-making.
7	Awan et al	2016	UK	The objective of her research is to find out the utility of online advertising to marketers and advertising agencies in their marketing goods.	Qualitative and quantitative research	The study discussed the outcomes, demonstrating that ads considerably impacted consumers' purchasing patterns and widened their decision-making.
8	Vijay & Balaji	2019	India	To analyze the reasons of online rather than in physical stores in India	Structured Interviews	The results demonstrated that Indian consumers purchase online due to convenience and time savings, but protection and privacy concerns prohibit them from doing so.
9	Kayumovich & Annamuradovna	2020	India	To do the comparative analysis of The internet marketing with traditional marketing	Comparative Analysis	The findings show that the traditional advertisement and marketing tactics have been surpassed by digital marketing.
10		2021	USA			

	Berkman & Gilson			To analyze the pattern of customers for making purchase decisions	Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis	Their study described as having "unified" behavior in customer's purchasing decision, based on the information they take in.
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Table 3. Digital communication as an advertising tool

Sl. No.	Author	Year	Location	Objective	Research Technique	Findings and Suggestions
1	Saxena, & Mittal	2017	India	To analyze Digital Advertising Techniques and Assessing its effectiveness	Quantitative and Qualitative both	The study concludes that digital advertising strategies such as "search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, e-mail marketing, and direct marketing" have become very common as a result of the association between technical innovation and online advertising.

2	Rathaur, & Agarwal	2019	India	To study the relationship between Content generation and management.	Exploratory(framing)	The study showcases that digital advertising drives the digitization process in India's digital economy.
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Conclusion

It is essential to identify the same information for the Indian e-commerce companies so that they can develop and implement effective strategies for fulfilling the same requirements. The findings of the study in the form of consumer behaviour over Buying Online Courses will certainly benefit the Indian e-commerce companies in attracting the attention of the local consumers towards their platforms for generating maximum revenue and refining the profits of India within the economy for providing certain stability and growth opportunities to the same.

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